

New Synthetic Biflavonyls

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Flavonols and 7-hydroxy flavone have been cross methylenated with methylene iodide to provide 3-7' biflavonyloxy methanes.

METHYLENATION of Flavonoids observed in nature¹⁻⁵ has also been carried out by Seshadri and coworkers⁶ in the laboratories, who reported the successful synthesis of biflavonyls in which the flavonoid units are interlinked through a methylenedioxy group, involving phenolic hydroxyl group at position 7 and 4' or through a methylene group between 5 and 8 positions. Biflavonyls in which two flavonoid units are interlinked through a methylenedioxy group but involving enolic hydroxyl group at position 3 of flavonols have been successfully synthesised in our laboratory^{7,8}. Similarly tri-flavonyloxy methanes^{8,9} have been synthesised by the methylation of flavonols with iodoform.

and the phenolic hydroxyl group of 7-hydroxy flavone. Flavonols (I), suitably substituted in 6 and 4' positions and 7-hydroxy flavone (II) have been cross methylenated by methylene iodide to Biflavonyloxy methanes (III).

Experimental (IIIa) :

Flavonol (1.0g) and 7-hydroxyflavone (1.0g) were refluxed in dry acetone (80 ml.) with methyleneiodide (1.4 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8g) for 36 hrs till a negative ferric chloride test was observed. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The potassium carbonate was washed

Now we have succeeded in synthesising, the so far unreported 3-7' biflavonyloxy methanes, involving the enolic hydroxyl group in the position 3 of flavonols

with acetone (20 × 3 ml.). The filtrate and the washing on recovery of the solvent provided a dark red viscous liquid which quickly solidified on cooling. Repeated crystallisations from benzene provided colourless needles (0.4g, 20%) m.p. 183°-84° (Found C 76.2; H, 4.2; mol. wt. 472; C₃₁H₂₀O₆ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.09%; mol. wt. 488). It's I. R. in KBr

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phase shows absorption bands at 3000, 1680, 1480, 1270, 1030 (due to methylenedioxy group). 900 and 770 cm^{-1} .

Compounds IIIb (m.p. $194^{\circ}\text{-}5^{\circ}$, yield 20%), IIIc (m.p. $217\text{-}218^{\circ}$, yield 20%) and IIId (m.p. $206\text{-}208^{\circ}$, yield 36%) were also synthesized in a similar manner and gave satisfactory elemental C/H analyses and I.R. spectra.

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